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Remembering Shiv K. Kumar as a Poet

**Sudhir K. Arora*

I have followed every funeral procession in town
of friend, relative or stranger –
for this is the moment of introspection.
Where does one go from here? (*Where Have the Dead Gone* 20)

...

So I have chosen to write hereafter
only on sand,
while I hear the waves
intoning mantras in my ears.
Let my epitaph be written on sand. (*Where Have the Dead Gone* 27)

...

Give me a line or two
in some local paper
even in fine print. (*Trapfalls in the Sky* 31)

While musing over the phenomenon of death and wondering where man goes after death, Shiv K. Kumar, whose first love is poetry, moved to the other world to experience 'Death' on March 1 2017. His death is an irreparable loss to every poetry lover though he is still alive through his creative writings, particularly poetry collections, namely, *Articulate Silences* (1970), *Cobwebs in the Sun* (1974), *Subterfuges* (1975), *Woodpackers*

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(1979) *Trapfalls in the Sky* (1986), *Woolgathering* (1995), *Thus Spake the Buddha* (2002), *Losing My Way* (2008), *Which of My Selves Do You Wish to Speak to?* (2011) and *Where Have the Dead Gone? & Other Poems* (2014). Today he is remembered as a poet though he endeavoured his hand in other genres like fiction, short-story, play and translation.

(II)

Shiv K. Kumar (1921-2017), a recipient of the Padma Bhusan, winner of Sahitya Akademi Award for his poetry collection—*Trapfalls in the Sky* in 1987, distinguished Professor of English, critic of great repute, Bergsonian scholar is an academic poet who has woven the texture of his poetry with intuitions, feelings, symbols, imagery and myths. D.H. Lawrence, T.S. Eliot and Bergson have influenced him so profoundly that he has developed a poetic attitude which recommends the primal innocence, purity and intuitions. The poet in Shiv K. Kumar rejects wickedness, reason, analysis and logic in favour of intuitions and innocence. He is sure that only intuitions help a man to face the challenges out of the predicaments in life. Reason and intellect fail to penetrate the mystery of life while intuitions offer the right vision to understand what life is. He feels that it is better to depend on intuition than merely on intellect or reason. Reflect over the excerpt from the poem 'He Walked All Night', which offers the poet's musings on life:

The best way to choose is not to choose
but just press on.
If you plan to return home,
it may take you a lifetime,
as reason stumbles at every step.
So why don't you rest through the day
and voyage through the night?' (*Where Have
the Dead Gone* 95)

(III)

Shiv K. Kumar's poetic idiom is touched with the West but the Western touch does not wipe out his Indian sensibility. The water of life flows in the Indian river with its western banks. Keki N. Daruwalla writes about Shiv K. Kumar's poetry saying: "It floats between ironic counterparts, and its tension comes from the Indian environment he writes in with an outlook moulded by years of living in the West" (110).

It is the force of Kumar's poetic idiom that makes even silent words speak. The words that lie in dormant stage come to action. The interweaving of words makes a poem alive. A solitary word does nothing but when it comes in touch with other words, it contributes in the poetic journey. All the words are charged with the pen of the poet who makes them sing and dance on the white sheet. He releases words softly. "Don't cough out words. / Just let them out softly" (*Losing My Way* 55). Images and figures come, react, interact and then, fuse. This happens by virtue of his poetic idiom which illumines words with insight. And this is how a poem takes birth.

A poem is born when words wing down
from the sky, chorusing like nightingales
with holes in their throats. (*Losing My
Way* 55)

Sometimes his poetry becomes confessional in tone. But, it is also true that a poet takes the raw material from his life. He cooks this raw material in the fire of imagination. He adds the spice of literary devices. It is the reader's participation which a poet longs for. He shares with Atma Ram thus:

I have been often labelled as a 'confessional' poet and indeed in tone and structure my poetry may be called 'autobiographical'. But what most readers fails to comprehend is the fact that a poet often invents facts

and experiences camouflaging them as real and authentic – to achieve the reader's total participation. It is more a strategy of the imagination than a transcript of empirical reality. (73)

(IV)

The poet peeps within to know who he is and why he has come here. He finds himself a bundle of various personalities. He delves deep to realise himself and explores his identity through love, sex, religion and landscapes. Many selves begin to pop out of him.

I am a beehive of selves
each conditioned by its own horoscope.
Touch me at any point
and I will metamorphose into a new
configuration
of colour and sound. (*Thus Spake the
Buddha* 17)

He debunks what is orthodox and outdated in religion. His progressive nature makes him satirize even social institutions like marriage. Intuitions, not religion is the right touchstone with which he judges a thing.

(V)

Buddha enters the poet Shiv K. Kumar and makes him somewhat philosophical in his approach towards life. He emphasizes on the sublimation of desires, not their suppression. The hunger is to be purified. When purified, it results in the creation like lava that licks earth and makes it fertile.

The way to satiate a yearning
is to sublimate it. Like lava licking
barren earth into tulips and marigolds. (*Thus
Spake the Buddha* 5)

With birth, death is certain. The body is a fort that has many exits. The body dies, not the soul. The soul remains

eternal. In the *Bhagavad Gita*, Lord Krishna says:

Nainam chhindanti shastraani nainam dahati
 paavakah;
 Na chainam kiedayantyaapo no shoshayati
 maarutah. (*Bhagavad Gita* 2.23)

Shiv K. Kumar who is influenced by the *Bhagavad-Gita* makes the people understand the truth of life and death. How philosophically yet plainly he states thus!

The body is like a fort, with many exits.
 When it crumbles under its own weight,
 the commander within flies away
 from the rear gate to set up another fort
 elsewhere. He is never killed.
 Flame cannot turn him to ashes,
 nor water dampen his resilience.
 He was there to see the first sunrise
 and he will survive to see this planet lapse
 into nothingness. (*Thus Spake the
 Buddha* 50)

When death is inevitable, why should it be feared? A man throughout his life remains greedy and collects one thing or the other in spite of knowing the fact that nothing will go with him in his journey beyond this world. Does it not seem to be strange that flesh is given to flame and ashes to the holy river? How philosophically the poet states the ultimate truth!

Perched on the wall a vulture cogitates
 upon human avidity—flesh offered
 to the flames, bones and ashes
 to the Ganges. No leaving
 for the living. (*Woodpeckers* 19)

Man should never forget the end. The moment of his painful journey begins the moment he comes in this world.

Pain, he has now learnt, is born
 in the mother's womb, and ends only

when the ashes are silenced—
 by a sprinkling of milk. (*Thus Spake the
 Buddha* 56)

It is strange that man suffers as a result of his sins committed in his previous life. Man continues to suffer without finding any solace. How painfully the poet has expressed the anguish of man!

Now the voyage of agony,
 from somewhere to nowhere,
 in search of redemption. (*Losing My Way* 26)

The poet desires to know the end of this painful voyage but finds himself perplexed as there is no way out of it. He is much influenced by the theory of Buddha who believes that pain is flowing in the world and its cause is desire.

(VI)

Shiv K. Kumar paints his poetic landscape with the colours of reality. Poverty and disease have become synonym with the lower poor class of the Indian society. These poor people are devoid of bread, clothes and shelter. The poet talks of street children, who have not any identity because “Identity is for those who lullabied / in cradles, and fed on / honey and dreams” (*Losing My Way* 41). But, these street children are denied name, honey and dreams. They are simply “leftovers in the dustbin, discarded even by a ragpicker” (*Losing My Way* 41). They are found before the churches and temples stretching their hands for bread or alms but fail to have from the devotees who come for worship. The poet believes that when the deities do not care for them, how will other people care?

I see them in front of churches
 and temples, their hands stretched
 out for boons. But who cares? Not even

the deities, each resting
smugly in his sanctorum. (*Losing My Way* 41)

If he writes on love and sex, he also writes on the underdog. In his poetry he talks of the street children, pavement sleepers, rickshaw pullers and the like. When it is night, these poor people sleep on the pavement without caring for tomorrow. The poet calls them fallen angels who come here only when the sun sets.

The poet believes that justice is always delayed. Man continues to move in and out of the court but never gets relief. The final relief that he gets is not from the court but from the court of God who calls him from the earth forever. This judicial system is polluted and poisonous to the extent that it snatches away man's precious time and, to the extreme, even life. One may come here but cannot go as there is no escape from its labyrinth. The only fate left to him is waiting. Waiting becomes life. Waiting becomes end.

It's the long wait that kills
the lover, the cancer-patient
and the petitioner. (*Trapfalls in the Sky* 23)

The petitioner continues to go in the hope of settlement or justice but gets date after date. Each date becomes another doomsday for him. He has to tolerate insult and alienation as soon as he enters it. The court spreads its labyrinth which never lets the petitioner go out of it.

During those aeons of anguish,
I seldom saw the Trinity, all together—
the judge, my counsel and the respondent.
So each time another doomsday was fixed
for my martyrdom. (*Woolgathering* 16)

The court becomes the grave for the alive. The petitioners become the living dead bodies. The judicial system is the river of pain which drowns petitioner and his family.

(VII)

Shiv K. Kumar is not against religion but he is against the irrational, outdated and orthodox rituals that have embraced religion in the name of faith and belief. He is against shedding blood of animal in the name of sacrifice for the goddess. What is the use of such sacrifices as take the lives of innocent animals like sheep? Does creation mean killing? The poet determines:

If the way to create
is the way to kill
I have hoarded enough blood
in my throat
for all the hyenas to suck from.

(*Subterfuges* 34)

The holy river Ganga is worshipped as a goddess among the Hindus who wish to die on her bank with the belief that they will go directly to heaven. The Ganga is religious to the extent that it lures even the poet to declare:

If I were to die
this is the moment
and this the place. (*Woolgathering* 23)

But, the poet cannot close his eyes to the pollution done in the name of religious rituals. Even the dead bodies, ashes and animals are thrown away into the river. It is strange that people take a bath for their outward purification without caring for the inner purification. With birth they enter the world as “chaste, like breast-milk” (*Trapfalls in the Sky* 35) but as the time passes they pollute themselves by becoming a part of pollution.

(VIII)

Shiv K. Kumar is a poet of love with a difference. He is natural in the matter of love and sex and, hence, expects

naturalness and openness. What he recommends is *samarpan*—total devotion. What's the use of sex if it is not done with love? Under the influence of D.H. Lawrence, he raises sex to the level of religion. He associates sex with religion through the instances of the Sun Temple, Konark and Khajuraho which highlight the religiosity of sex. He gives wings to the holy sex and takes the reader to Khajuraho where various gods and goddesses are seen in different sexual postures which give a feel of creation and divine energy. Man is alive because of love and sex. Man exists because sex exists. Sex is the holy flame which continues to illumine the way that finally elevates him to the divine within. What Khajuraho has become today is the result of sculptor's intuitive hands. Reason makes distance while intuition lessens it. Stones at Khajuraho cannot tolerate any control; they remain free and so seem to be engaged in love-making.

Since any distance
 between leaf and bud, bone and flesh
 hand and breast, only whets appetite
 these stones brook no restraint .
 They flow into a confluence of navels,
 Legs and thighs, leaving blemishes
 Even on a lotus palm. (*Woolgathering* 24)

(IX)

The poet is not a slave of an institution like marriage for love. A true relationship depends on mutual understanding and caring. The marriage ceremony can bind two individuals officially but not necessarily internally. He wonders that before marriage how love can be lust and after marriage how lust turns itself into love. He sees the birds while mating in the tree's foliage which provide a cover for "the ritual of love." The other thing that he traces in birds mating is that they are

detached and not bound with any bond for the whole life. One bird hops onto the other and after performing sex act it flies away without the possibility of reunion with the same one. The poet knows that attachment brings pain. When it brings pain, why does a man not seek freedom—freedom from the bond of living for life? He is against hypocrisy and double standard of the people who believe in the continuation of the bond despite the lack of faith and mutual understanding in love. Birds are better than human beings as they are not attached to their companions because they know that the attachment will result in pain, suffering and separation. Mark the excerpt from the poem “Birds Mating”, which exposes hypocrisy of the human beings in the name of love on one side and philosophy of detachment on other side though the way does not suit to Indian values and traditions:

As each bird flies away to its own hemisphere,
 there will be no reunion hereafter —
 never the same tree, nor the same pair.
 If attachment breeds pain,
 why not seek peace in freedom?
 If the same river flows into the same sea,
 the waters would turn turbid. (*Where Have
 the Dead Gone* 86)

(X)

Shiv K. Kumar is wrongly alleged for being anti-women while the truth is that he criticises only the inconstant and infidel women. He respects woman as woman—be she a prostitute, mango-vender or female jogger or maid-servant or any other female form. He respects women with faith and constancy. He appreciates Indian women for their faith and patience that they have for their husbands. India is considered to be “triple-baked Continent” because, as Prabhat K. Singh writes, “Life in

India is baked in the fires of sun, sex and penury” (106). The poet has compared them to empty pitchers waiting for their husband who will come and fill their heart with love.

In this triple-baked Continent
 women don't etch angry eyebrows
 on mud walls.
 Patiently they sit
 like empty pitchers
 on the mouth of the village well
 pleating hope in each braid
 of their Mississippi-long hair
 looking deep into the water's mirror
 for the moister in their eyes. (*Cobwebs in the Sun* 4)

The poet in Shiv K. Kumar pleads the case of woman before God though he remains quite opposed to her for her faithlessness and infidelity. Generally, he respects woman in woman and asks God to see this creation made out of him. Is it really sin on his part if he has pressed her to his bosom with the intention of reclaiming the bone out of which she was created? Praising her he pleads her case before God thus:

Look at this woman you created
 out of me. A marvel, isn't she? A symphony
 of design and aroma. A rose-bush grown out
 of
 my rib's seedling. Temptation even for your
 angels to deny you, at least for a night.
 Was it a sin if I pressed her to my bosom?
 May be I was just reclaiming my lost rib.
 (*Losing My Way* 6)

(XI)

Shiv K. Kumar is a fine craftsman who chisels his verse with his poetic tools like figures, paradoxes, contrasts,

irony and satire. His academic brain makes the abstract concrete. He is not for an ordinary reader. His poetry needs a reader with discipline, wit and understanding. He interrogates and leaves the reader to opt the best alternatives as suggested through the paradoxes and contrasts. The use of paradox makes him impartial and objective. He himself states: “peach paradox carries two faces: / fruit and worm, beginning and end” (*Thus Spake the Buddha* 44). His figures are telling and pictorial.

Simile:

The air is calm
like a bird frozen on its wings.
So is the lake napping
like a crocodile on the sand. (*Thus Spake the Buddha* 37)

Metaphor:

The moon, veiled partially
by a cloud’s hem, is a slice
of some water-melon. (*Thus Spake the Buddha* 55)

Beautiful blending of Personification with Simile:

A shadow
crouches on the earth like a predator
in search of its prey—consciousness
retreating within itself. (*Losing My Way* 8)

The poet uses the art of rhetoric when he articulates through questioning. For instance:

But how can you confront the sun
if you don’t seek rebirth after each death?
(*Woolgathering* 67)

Doesn’t sinning carry within its womb
the seeds of redemption? (*Losing My Way* 7)

His phrases like “involutions of pain” (*Articulate Silences* 11), “silken thighs” (*Articulate Silences* 21), “seductive

movements” (*Articulate Silences* 26), “pregnant folly” (*Cobwebs in the Sun* 32) and “the vaginal creeks” (*Cobwebs in the Sun* 48) are well-crafted and picturesque. Being an academic poet he knows the art of generalization out of particular situations. Here are two beautiful excerpts that illustrate his art of generalisation:

The moment of despair
has no age
no discretion. (*Woodpeckers* 39)

Often the moment of pain seeks solace
in a headstone, not tears. (*Trapfalls in the Sky* 27)

The use of proverbial lines strikes the reader who cannot remain without praising him for the striking lines. Here are two instances of such proverbial lines:

Attachment generates only anguish. (*Thus Spake the Buddha* 57)

A destination is often a mirage. (*Losing My Way* 40)

The poet has employed images after images which become imprinted on the mind of the reader as soon as he deciphers them. These images make the invisible visible. The abstracts become concrete.

(XII)

Shiv K. Kumar is a poet of love and intuitions. It is only he who can see the holy Ganga in the West and Mississippi in the East. Sex, to him, is not a means to release lust but a religious mantra that can make one feel divine. No doubt, his poems make a show of breasts, lips and thighs but this show makes the reader serious to life which is meant to live lively and intuitively under any circumstances. He respects women but does not fail to criticize the faithless ones. He gives due place to the

cries of the poor and the exploited. He satirizes the corrupt judicial system that offers nothing except pain and suffering. The pen is dipped in the satirical ink which writes nothing but the truth though somewhere the intention of amelioration for the greater cause is reflected. Life is boring but he motivates to make it colourful with the aesthetic specs. Lust makes one fall while love makes one rise. He has written the script of intuitions but this layered script requires equally the reader's cerebrum for deciphering. The script of intuitions inspires to love—love mixed with harmony of body, mind and soul. He dips in the river of love and inspires others to be in this river. This river is polluted when one takes a dip with lust. Divine love is experienced when one takes a dip with the total surrender. This divine love survives even after death. This is the only valuable possession that counts. Though the poet is no more, he survives by virtue of this divine love which he recommended along with his emphasis on intuitions. The poet in Shiv K. Kumar articulates the inarticulate truth thus:

What will survive
beyond the tombstone is only divine love.
(*Losing My Way* 42)

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